

**Biogeographical classification of Austria based on
hierarchical cluster analysis of vascular plant distributions**

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Fig. S1: Cluster dendrogram based on Ward method and Euclidean distance. Blue rectangles indicate clusters at cutlevel 25.

Fig. S2: Cluster dendrogram based on Complete Linkage method and Euclidean distance. Blue rectangles indicate clusters at cutlevel 25.

Fig. S3: Cluster dendrogram based on Complete Linkage method and Jaccard index. Blue rectangles indicate clusters at cutlevel 25.

Fig. S4: Cluster dendrogram based on Complete Linkage method and Dice index. Blue rectangles indicate clusters at cutlevel 25.

Fig. S5: Geographic delimitation of clusters identified at cutlevel 25 based on Ward method and Euclidean distance.

Fig. S6: Geographic delimitation of clusters identified at cutlevel 25 based on Complete Linkage method and Euclidean distance.

Fig. S7: Geographic delimitation of clusters identified at cutlevel 25 based on Complete Linkage method and Jaccard index.

Fig. S8: Geographic delimitation of clusters identified at cutlevel 25 based on Complete Linkage method and Dice index.

Fig. S9: NbClust diagram, Krzanowski and Lai Index (Ward method, Euclidean distance).